

Handout and Worksheet Motivational Design - further study

Keller (2009): ARCS Model of Motivational Design

Retrieved 20.12.2021 from:

https://books.google.de/books?id=HRCQIzZMwhsC&pg=PA43&hl=de&source=gbs_toc_r&cad=3#v=onepage&q&f=false

Major Categories and Definitions		Process Questions
Attention	Capturing the interest of learners; stimulating the curiosity to learn	How can I make this learning experience stimulating and interesting?
Relevance	Meeting the personal needs/ goals of the learner to effect a positive attitude	In what ways will this learning experience be valuable for my students?
Confidence	Helping the learners believe/ feel that they will succeed and control their success	How can I via instruction help the students succeed and allow them to control their success?
Satisfaction	Reinforcing accomplishment with rewards (internal and external)	What can I do to help the students feel good about their experience and desire to continue learning?

Table 3.1 ARCS Model Categories, Definitions, and Process Questions (Keller, 2009)

Keller, J. M. (2009). *Motivational Design for Learning and Performance: The ARCS Model Approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, New York, USA, p. 45, Table 3.1

Keller suggests to follow these 10 steps as a systematic process of Motivational Design (Keller, 2009, pp. 57 ff.):

1. Obtain course information
2. Obtain audience information
3. Analyze audience
4. Analyze existing materials
5. List objectives and assessments
6. List potential tactics*
7. Select and design tactics*
8. Integrate with instruction
9. Select and develop materials
10. Evaluate and revise

*The tactics mentioned in steps 6 and 7 refer to A, R, C, S

Task for Further Study

Please focus Step 7 in Keller's suggestions: 7. Select and design tactics*, with the 'tactics' referring to the points portrayed in the A, R, C, S Model:

A – Attention **R** – Relevance **C** – Confidence **S** – Satisfaction

Now write down first ideas as examples of how to include these points in your course- & lesson planning.